

Gravimetric Estimation of Vanadium with *o*-Hydroxyacetophenone Oxime

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There are few organic reagents which have so far been reported for the gravimetric estimation of vanadium by direct weighing of the precipitate. *o*-Hydroxyacetophenone oxime has been found to be a quite satisfactory reagent for this purpose. The precipitation of the red-brown vanadium compound by this reagent is complete between pH 2.2 and 4.8. After drying at 110°, the precipitate corresponds to the composition $\text{VO(OH)(C}_8\text{H}_9\text{O}_2\text{N)}_2$.

The precipitation was carried out at temperatures not exceeding 35-40°, as at higher temperatures the metal was reduced to the lower valence states by the reagent. Metallic elements like nickel, cobalt, zinc, cadmium, lead, mercury, manganese, molybdenum, chromium, tungsten, and uranium as well as phosphoric and arsenic acids do not interfere. Iron(III), when present, was masked by adding phosphoric acid. Copper, palladium, and titanium interfere and should be removed before estimating vanadium. Oxalates, tartrates, and fluorides also hinder the precipitation.

A 2% ethanolic solution of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone oxime was used. A standard vanadium solution was prepared by dissolving an weighed amount of ammonium metavanadate in distilled water containing a little ammonia. The vanadium content of the solution was determined by evaporating an aliquot portion of the solution to dryness and then igniting it to V_2O_5 . All chemicals used were of A. R. or G. R. quality.

The precipitation of vanadium by the reagent was found to depend on the pH of the solution. At pH 2.2 to 4.8 and temperature not exceeding 30-35°, vanadium is completely precipitated as a reddish brown precipitate which can be washed with water and dried to a constant weight, the factor being 0.1327.

It was found that precipitation of vanadium with *o*-hydroxyacetophenone oxime was complete only when an excess of about 2.5 times the stoichiometric amount of the reagent was used.